

CITY-MOVE

City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health

HORIZON-HLTH-2023-DISEASE-03

D(7.3): Data Management Plan

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Summary Sheet

Deliverable Number	D7.3
Deliverable Name	Data Management Plan
Full Project Title	CITY-MOVE: City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health
Responsible Author(s)	De Deurwaerder, Oberon
Contributing Partner(s)	UA
Peer Review	Peeters, Jef
Contractual Delivery Date	30-06-2025
Actual Delivery Date	01-07-2025
Status	Living document
Dissemination level	Public
Version	V2
No. of Pages	18
WP/Task related to the deliverable	WP 7 / Task 7.2 – 7.3
WP/Task responsible	Van Olmen, Josefien
Document ID	CITY-MOVE_D7.3_DMP
Abstract	Data Management Plan as living document regarding the City-Move Project.

Legal Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The City-Move project aims to collect and analyze data to evaluate the effectiveness of urban policies on physical activity (PA) behaviors in six partner cities: Antwerp, Bogotá, Kampala, Lima, Ljubljana, and Rotterdam. This data management plan outlines the approach for gathering and utilizing both primary and secondary data to inform policy makers and promote PA worldwide. Primary data collection will involve stakeholder interviews, surveys, and community asset maps. Interviews will be semi-structured, capturing audio recordings and transcripts, and will provide insights into PA policy and urban planning. Surveys will be conducted with stakeholders involved in PA interventions, yielding text data. Community asset maps will be created to visually represent the PA policy ecosystem in each city. Secondary data will include government datasets, open-source information, and satellite images.

The expected data assets include community asset maps, TIDieR checklists, stakeholder surveys, interview transcripts, weighting data from interviews and workshops, and knowledge and skills surveys. All data will be managed according to FAIR principles, ensuring it is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers such as DOIs will be assigned to datasets, and rich metadata will be provided to facilitate discovery and reuse. Metadata will include comprehensive descriptions, keywords, and context for the data, enhancing its utility and discoverability.

Data will be deposited in trusted repositories like Zenodo, adhering to open access principles. Personal data will be pseudonymised and/or anonymized where possible, with restricted access to sensitive data. Metadata will be openly available under a Creative Commons Zero (CC-0) license. The project emphasizes making data as open as possible while respecting legal and ethical considerations. No embargoes are anticipated for data publication, ensuring timely availability for reuse. The data will remain accessible and findable for the long term.

Data quality will be assured through rigorous management practices, including validation, verification, and regular reviews. The project aims to enhance data utility for policymakers and researchers by providing a detailed understanding of PA interventions in urban contexts. The plan includes provisions for curation, storage, and long-term preservation, with costs covered by the Horizon Europe grant. The University of Antwerp's DMP-support team, along with the project manager and researchers, will oversee the implementation of the data management plan, ensuring compliance with ethical standards and maximizing the impact of the collected data.

1. DATA SUMMARY

1.1. INTRODUCTION AND SCOPE

The purpose of collecting data in City-Move is to achieve a better understanding of the effectiveness and impact of urban policy on the physical activity (PA) behaviours on the affected citizens. We aim to achieve a holistic and ecological understanding of PA-interventions and their effects on the health of individuals living in an urban environment in each of the six partner cities, being Antwerp (Belgium), Bogotá (Colombia), Kampala (Uganda), Lima (Peru), Ljubljana (Slovenia) and Rotterdam (Netherlands). The different data types and formats to be used will vary both in format, origin, and novelty. Overall, we expect the data gathered to be useful both for future research endeavours, on both the national or international level, and to inform policy makers and professionals active in promoting PA worldwide.

In the early stages of the project it is difficult to provide an estimate of the projected size of the data to be gathered. We can briefly divide the type of data in two main categories. First there is the primary data collection to be conducted by the different researchers and their respective project tasks. This data will consist of interviews with stakeholders in each of the partner cities, transcripts of interviews, reports from living lab experiments and surveys conducted in all cities. As this data gathering process involves mapping out who the relevant stakeholders to interview in each city are, it is currently still to be determined how many interviewees there will be and how large the data will be gathered through this process. The second data gathering aspect will consist of understanding and sourcing routine data gathered by the partner cities, relevant to a holistic understanding of PA. The aim of this part of the project is to contribute to as granular and detailed as possible longitudinal understanding of the effects of PA interventions in each city. Herein the project will source data gathered by the cities and select which sources are relevant and informative, however, this does not per se mean that all relevant sources will be copied or used in full for the project. Like the primary data collection part, it would therefore currently be inaccurate to make estimates on the size of the data collected.

An overview of the data expected to be produced through City-Move can be found in table 1 below.

Table 1: Overview of data assets to be produced

Dataset	Quantity	WP
Community asset maps	1 per intervention = 13 maps	1
Completed TIDieR checklist	1 per intervention = 13 checklists	3
Surveys stakeholders for late interventions (7)	100 stakeholders per intervention = 700 surveys	3
Interviews with stakeholders in all interventions (13)	20 stakeholders per intervention = 260 transcripts	1-3
Interviews with city data stakeholders	10 stakeholders per city = 60 transcripts	4
Data on weightings (from interviews & workshop)	1 weighting set per intervention city = 12 sets	5
Data from knowledge and skills survey	200 stakeholders per region = 600 surveys	6

1.2. TYPES OF DATA

1.2.1. Primary data sources

1.2.1.1. Stakeholder interviews

Through different work packages, stakeholders engaged in different aspects of PA policy will be interviewed. The format of the interviews is planned to be semi-structured, starting from a fixed list of questions but allowing the participants to expand on their views, opinions, personal experience and expertise. These interviews will result in two types of data, being audio recordings and their corresponding transcripts in text format. As this is data gathered by our team of researchers, we label this as primary data. In terms of data utility, we expect this data to be useful for researchers investigating PA and prevention of non-communicable diseases, as well as researchers trying to understand urban planning and PA-related policy. For governments and policy in general, we expect the results of these interviews to be informative for all policymakers globally trying to encourage PA in their respective jurisdiction.

1.2.1.2. Survey stakeholders for late interventions

A second part of primary data collection is done by asking the identified broader stakeholders active around urban-setting PA to fill in a survey. This survey already has been created and is currently being approved and translated by the partner universities involved. The resulting data of this survey will be in text format, and relatively small in size by our current estimates.

1.2.1.3. Community asset maps

A third and for now last type of primary data to be collected is a detailed map of the relevant stakeholders within each partner city. The format of this map will be a simple spreadsheet, although a visual representation of the layers, affiliations and responsibilities can be included as well. The stakeholder maps are a synthesis of both the aforementioned interviews and survey results, and will provide a high-level overview of the PA policy ecosystem in each partner city.

1.2.2. Secondary data sources

By secondary (and tertiary if needed and available) data we mean government data sources, possibly from the partner cities themselves or affiliated government agencies, and publicly available open-source data, such as satellite imagery or information published by NGO's. We will gather and describe secondary data sources for two reasons. First, to attain a longitudinal understanding of PA interventions and an assessment of their effects, the project will require data preceding the start of the research. Second, the aim of City-Move is to provide recommendations to policy makers on how to improve the effects and impact of their efforts, in which understanding the way routine data is gathered and how it can be improved is an essential part. These sources can take the form of regular datasets, geographic data structures including polygons and coordinate information, (satellite) imagery, data from air quality sensors, and so on.

As the size and scope of finding useful secondary data sources gathered by the cities and moreover, identifying where comparable data is lacking, is an intrinsic goal of the research project, this list is not finite, neither can the size of the resulting totality of data used be properly estimated at this point of the project.

1.3. FURTHER DETAILS

1.3.1. Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

As described in detail in 1.2.2, we will need to (re-)use existing data as this forms an intrinsic part of the purpose of the project. We will expand further on this throughout the course of the research. Regarding the primary data collection, we believe that establishing a baseline of primary information through the interviews with relevant stakeholders and accompanying survey is imperative. The consortium is however aware of extant research in the discipline and is happy and willing to include existing data sources wherever they prove useful.

1.3.2. What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Referring to the introduction in part 1.1, the purpose of City-Move is to understand, improve and implement PA interventions in an urban context. In order to achieve this goal, we seek to understand the stakeholders in each city, to be able to create active societies, active people.

1.3.3. What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

As was discussed in the listing of the different types of data we aim to gather and re-use, the size of the resulting datasets will vary greatly on, for primary data, the size of the network of professionals and more general stakeholders active around PA policy in each partner city, and for secondary data, on the data sources provided by each city – to the level it is useful for the City-Move project to physically store these datasets itself. For more general, second or third party data, such as satellite imagery, the datasets can take a substantial size if it is necessary to store open-source data on a local (or cloud) machine for analysis. As these sources are by definition publicly available, it has to be determined whether it's useful and relevant to copy the original datasets into a separate repository, or only provide the existing repositories or sources and provide the analysis process, whether in code or in other form. Therefore, better estimates of the size of the aforementioned data can be made further in the process.

1.3.4. What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

We refer to the listing of different data types provided in paragraph 1.2, where was illustrated that the provenance is twofold. For primary data, being the interviews, surveys and stakeholder maps, the origin of the data is direct, meaning we're conducting primary data collection not depending on outside sources. For the secondary data used and necessary for City-Move, the provenance is diverse. In sourcing data directly from the partner cities, we expect to encounter a mixture of data routinely gathered by the cities themselves, regarding the urban context in which they operate. Some of these sources will be sourced on the city level, other will be provided by higher-level government instances, such as a national bureau of statistics. We also deem it possible that lower-level government instances, for example on a district or neighbourhood level, can be data sources used.

Moving on to other secondary types of data, we can list a non-conclusive overview of possible data sources and their origins, however, it is too early at the moment of writing to indicate which of these sources will actually be used for the research. We note:

- Publicly available satellite imagery, coming from academic, national or international organizations, such as UNAVCO or NASA.

- Publicly available datasets from NGO's collecting data on the international level, such as the Demographic Health Surveys (DHS Program).
- Any source providing comparable, preferably longitudinal, data on environmental factors such as air quality (e.g. the World Air Pollution Index Project or WAQI), noise pollution, and on PA levels in a given partner city.

As this list is not conclusive, we'd like to make the concluding statement that the purpose of the secondary data gathering is built specifically around creating a comprehensive, comparable and longitudinal image of each partner city through data, in which the sources of the data used can be wide and diverse, but will always be assessed on their quality and trustworthiness.

1.3.5. To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Regarding data utility, the resulting overview and mixture of primary data being collected and secondary data being mapped, will be useful for both policymakers and researchers alike. The project is unique in that sense that it studies the differences between cities in Low- and Middle Income countries (LMIC's) versus cities in high-income countries (HIC's), and is the first of its kind that attempts to make an intercontinental, longitudinal assessment of the effect of PA interventions in an urban context. We therefore expect both the results of our research and the data gathered and mapped to be of interest to anyone wanting to improve PA policy, and to anyone researching PA policy interventions.

2. FAIR PRINCIPLES

2.1. FAIR PRINCIPLES: MAKING DATA FINDABLE

2.1.1. Will data and other research outputs be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes, persistent identifiers (PIDs) will be allocated to all data and research outputs, ensuring their long-term accessibility and traceability. Data sets and other research outputs will be assigned Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) upon deposition in trusted repositories, such as Zenodo. Additionally, authors involved in the action will be identified using ORCID or ResearcherID. Organizations and the grant itself will also be assigned persistent identifiers, utilizing ROR IDs for organizations and grant DOIs for grants. A permanent and unique identifier will be provided for all published datasets (findability). All data will be published under a Creative Commons Zero (CC-0) license to ensure maximal legal interoperability. Datasets containing personal data, such as interview

transcripts and survey datasets will be anonymised to the extent possible. If full anonymization is possible, they will be published openly. If not, the data will be deposited in a closed-access repository with openly published metadata to ensure findability and citeability. The metadata will include conditions and access request procedure. Codebooks used for analysis will be published in Zenodo and will include definitions of codes and clear documentation of the analysis procedure. Metadata of datasets will refer to the codebooks used.

2.1.2. Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery?

Rich metadata will indeed be provided to facilitate discovery and reuse of the data. Metadata accompanying each dataset will include comprehensive descriptions ensuring contextual understanding and interpretation. Specifically, metadata will encompass details such as project identifier (including title, funding acknowledgment, and grant number), dataset title, description (methodology employed and city of origin), DOI, sample identifier (anonymized for interviewees and participants), link to data storage, documentation of the dataset (e.g., interview or survey questions/protocols, date, time, and place), confidentiality status and access rights, file format, dates of issue and last modification, and contact information. These metadata standards adhere to established conventions within the field and comply with FAIR principles to maximize data discoverability and usability.

2.1.3. Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes, search keywords will be included in the metadata to enhance discoverability and potential reuse of the data. These keywords will be meticulously selected to accurately reflect the content and scope of each dataset, thereby facilitating efficient retrieval by interested parties. By incorporating relevant keywords into the metadata, we aim to streamline the process of data discovery and promote its subsequent utilization across diverse research contexts.

2.1.4. Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes, metadata will be structured and formatted in a manner conducive to harvesting and indexing, ensuring seamless integration into existing data repositories and search engines. By adhering to established metadata standards and formats, our datasets will be readily ingestible by indexing systems, thus maximizing their visibility and accessibility within the scholarly community and beyond. This approach underscores our commitment to fostering open science practices and facilitating widespread dissemination of research outcomes.

2.2. FAIR PRINCIPLES: MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

2.2.1. Will the data and other research outputs be deposited in a trusted repository?

Yes, all data and research outputs generated by CITY-MOVE will be deposited in trusted repositories in accordance with the requirements outlined by Horizon Europe. We are committed to making our data findable and accessible by adhering to the principles of open science. Specifically, our data will be deposited in certified repositories such as Zenodo, which aligns with internationally recognized standards for data preservation and dissemination. Zenodo, being a disciplinary and domain repository endorsed by research communities, ensures the assignment of persistent identifiers (DOIs) to facilitate long-term accessibility and citation of our datasets. By leveraging trusted repositories like Zenodo, we aim to enhance the discoverability and reusability of our research outputs, thereby fostering transparency and collaboration within the scientific community. Through carefully curating the personal identifiers possibly included in qualitative data, we plan to comply with the requirements for privacy protection while adhering to the FAIR principles.

2.2.2. Accessibility of data/research outputs

2.2.2.1. Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data and other research outputs will be deposited?

At this stage, no specific arrangements have been made with our identified repository where our data will be stored.

2.2.2.2. Does the repository ensure that the data and other research outputs are assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes, we will work with a unique persistent identifier (DOI) assigned by the repository to ensure long-term accessibility and citation of our datasets.

2.2.2.3. Will all data and other research outputs be made openly available?

Here we work according to the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, as we also described in the Horizon proposal. All data without legal, contractual, or ethical restrictions, along with the documentation and metadata, will be made available in an open data repository per Open Access and FAIR principles following the timescales established in the Data Management Plan (D7.2, D7.3). A permanent and unique identifier will be provided for all published datasets (findability). All data will be published under a Creative Commons Zero (CC-0) license to ensure maximal legal interoperability. Datasets containing personal data, such as interview transcripts and survey datasets, will be pseudonymised to the extent possible. If full anonymization is possible, they will be published openly. If not, the data will be deposited in a closed-access repository with openly published metadata to ensure findability and citeability. The metadata will include conditions and access request procedure.

2.2.2.4. Is an embargo applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents)?

No, at this point there are no actions or deliverables laid out that would require the protection of intellectual property outside of the normal authorship protection. All project deliverables and outputs will be screened for IP protection needs, prior to publication and all involved partners will agree on plans for dissemination and/or exploitation. IP will be managed throughout the project through the IP register, as part of this data management plan.

2.2.2.5. Will the data and other research outputs be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Yes, the City-Move consortium will make sure that all data and research outputs are freely accessible, in a standardized manner. This is on the one hand ensured by the Horizon protocol, guaranteeing open access of the deliverables produced in City-Move. On the other hand, by publishing the data assets on the Zenodo platform, we will ensure the openness and accessibility.

2.2.2.6. How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

When working with a trusted repository such as Zenodo, the identification and verification of the individuals accessing the datasets and outputs lies with the operators of the repository. A person We will put in place an access request system so that individuals interested in the (publicly accessible) data inform us about their interest for the data assets. Their identity then is verified by logging in to the repository before being able to request the data.

2.2.2.7. Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

At this stage of the project, we do not see the need for a separate data access committee to be established. Personal identifiers are not to be included in the published parts of the datasets, the nature of the data assets itself does not require ethical or security considerations.

2.2.2.8. Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why.

Yes, such as per the grant agreement, metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), we do not wish or plan to deviate from this requirement.

2.2.2.9. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes, metadata of all data assets produced and published will be available and will allow for access to the data. Examples are links to the corresponding data assets or platforms provided by a local government, the researchers within the team responsible for the specific data asset, or the name of the data source.

2.2.2.10. How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Following the common practice within the field of public health and population health, we aim to keep the data publicly online and available for at least 20 years, both for the data assets themselves as for the metadata.

2.2.2.11. Will documentation or reference about any software needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We note that for the Zenodo platform, having internet access and a browser, plus the knowledge on how to use both, suffice to access the platform online. On the Zenodo website, there is documentation available on how to use the platform itself. For code written by the consortium, we will provide a document containing the needed dependencies for a user to be able to read and use the code. For now ^{we} do not plan on providing information on how to read or use this code, as the incapacity to use a program or interface to read code also means that what we publish will not be readable by that specific user. We will include a README-file to provide instructions for readers on what requirements in terms of software packages and libraries are required for running our scripts. General tutorials however on how to for example use R or Python are widely available for free online and will do a better job at explaining the use of these programming languages than the CITY-MOVE consortium can explain. We of course do not have any intention of restricting access with this statement, as our outputs and data processing methods will be transparent and shared online.

2.3. FAIR PRINCIPLES: MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

2.3.1. Will your data and other research outputs include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Yes, as described above, where data is already available we will include the official links to the appropriate databases or repositories. Part of the work to be done is making an overview of these databases, and so we will be happy to share our findings and create meaningful links between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. We for instance work with a common core list of abbreviations, shared across the whole project, will helps readers to get acquainted with the subject-specific vocabulary.

2.3.2. General interoperability remarks

We need to first and foremost make our data interoperable for our own team. From this perspective, we will resort as much as possible to generally readable file formats and output formats. This ensures that anyone with a computer can open and read our files. Yes we will use the most common vocabulary possible. We for instance

work with a common core list of abbreviations, shared across the whole project, will help readers to get acquainted with the subject-specific vocabulary.

2.4. FAIR PRINCIPLES: MAKING DATA RE-USABLE

2.4.1. How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

All data will be licensed under a Creative Commons Zero (CC-0) license to ensure maximal legal interoperability. This will allow the widest possible re-use of the data by removing all restrictions on the use of the datasets.

2.4.2. When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Data will be made available for re-use as soon as possible following the timescales established in the Data Management Plan (D7.2, D7.3). No embargo is currently anticipated.

2.4.3. Are the data produced and/or used in the project usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Yes, all data produced and used in the project will be usable by third parties, particularly after the end of the project, except where restrictions are necessary for legal, contractual, or ethical reasons. In cases where data must be closed or restricted, the metadata will still be findable and accessible to enable potential re-use under appropriate conditions.

2.4.4. How long will the data be re-usable?

Following the common practice within the field of public health and population health, we aim to keep the data publicly online and available for at least 20 years.

2.4.5. Will data quality be assessed/assured?

Yes, the data quality will be assessed and assured through the implementation of robust data management practices, including thorough data validation and verification processes. This will involve cross-checking data for accuracy, consistency, and completeness, as well as regular reviews and updates to ensure the data remains relevant and reliable.

2.4.6. Further comments on re-usability

To facilitate the re-usability of data, we will provide comprehensive documentation and metadata alongside the datasets. This will include detailed descriptions of the data collection methods, processing procedures, and any relevant contextual information to ensure that third parties can effectively understand and utilize the data. Additionally, we will encourage and support the use of our data in new research, applications, and services to maximize its impact and value to the wider community.

3. RESOURCES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

3.1. CURATION AND STORAGE/PRESERVATION COSTS

Making research data/outputs FAIR involves several costs, including curation, storage, and preservation. The primary costs will be associated with:

- Data Curation: Ensuring data quality and interoperability.
- Storage: Using trusted repositories like Zenodo, which may have associated storage costs depending on the volume of data.
- Preservation: Long-term storage to maintain data accessibility for at least 20 years.

Note that costs related to data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions), and are budgeted in the proposal.

3.2. DATA MANAGEMENT

3.2.1. Person/team responsible for data management and quality assurance

The data management and quality assurance will be overseen by the team members of CITY-MOVE responsible for the DMP. This consists of the project manager, the DMP-support team of the University of Antwerp and the researchers involved.

3.2.2. Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

As mentioned before, the combined team of the project manager, the DMP support of the University of Antwerp, and the researchers responsible for the DMP within the City-Move team.

3.2.3. How will long term preservation be ensured

Long-term preservation will be ensured through:

- **Trusted Repositories:** Utilizing repositories like Zenodo that are designed for long-term data preservation.
- **Persistent Identifiers:** Assigning DOIs to datasets to ensure their persistent accessibility.
- **Regular Backups:** Conducting regular backups and data integrity checks to prevent data loss.
- **Compliance with Standards:** Following international standards for data preservation to maintain data usability over time.

3.3. DATA SECURITY

3.3.1. What provisions are or will be in place for data security?

We are aware of the risk of repeating ourselves, however, for completeness: thanks to the use of a trusted repository that guarantees the encryption, safe storage and possibility to recover data in case of loss, we briefly describe the security provisions provided:

- **Data Encryption:** Encrypting data during transfer and at rest to prevent unauthorized access, provided by the trusted repositories we work with.
- **Secure Storage:** Storing data in secure, access-controlled environments.
- **Data Recovery:** Implementing regular backups and disaster recovery plans to ensure data can be restored in case of loss. This covers both back-ups preserved locally on the computers of the machines and servers of the research team, as well as the back-ups provided by our trusted repository.
- **Access Controls:** Limiting data access to authorized personnel only, based on their roles and responsibilities. For parties outside of the research team, requiring identification and placing an access request before being granted access.

3.3.2. Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes, as the general guidelines mentioned above, prescribe.

3.4. ETHICS

3.4.1. Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

There could be ethical and legal issues related to data sharing, particularly concerning the privacy and confidentiality of personal data collected during the project. These issues will be addressed by:

- **Informed Consent:** Obtaining informed consent from participants for data sharing and long-term preservation.
- **Anonymization:** Anonymizing data wherever possible to protect participant identities, where possible. Especially for qualitative data, this might prove tricky and a case-to-case evaluation needs to be done.
- **Pseudonymization:** As qualitative data often can be rendered useless when anonymizing the personal identifiers, a process of pseudonymization can help preserve the value of these data assets while protecting the privacy of participants involved.
- **Legal Compliance:** Adhering to relevant data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR) to ensure legal compliance in data handling and sharing.

We discuss the ethics considerations in further detail in the separate ethics approval document from the consortium.

3.4.2. Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Yes.

3.5. OTHER ISSUES / DMP DETAILS

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

We use SharePoint for general, day-to-day sharing of working files and documents. These adhere to the internal data protection plans of the respective universities of the team.

3.5.1. European Commission (Horizon): Horizon Europe DMP + - DPIA

DPIA: Have you performed a DPIA for the personal data processing activities for this project?

We don't consider this per se applicable for our project. We will review the possible relevance of performing a DPIA in a later phase of the project, when we might run into sensitive information during or after the stakeholder interviews.

3.5.2. European Commission (Horizon): Horizon Europe DMP + - Full DMP

Version information

Action number: 101136358

Action acronym: City-Move

Action title: City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health

DMP version number: V1.0

Date: 26/03/2024

Have you registered personal data processing activities for this project?

No, this has not been deemed necessary at this point of the project.